

LOAN SERVICES OF COOPERATIVES AND THE SUSTAINABILITY OF LIVELIHOOD PROGRAMS TO THEIR MEMBERS IN TACURONG CITY

Norigen Domile Diesto
Adonis S. Besa, PhD

Sultan Kudarat State University, ACCESS, EJC Montilla, Tacurong City, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the relationship between cooperative loan services and the sustainability of livelihood programs among members in Tacurong City, Philippines. Cooperatives serve as vital financial institutions for marginalized communities, offering credit, savings, microfinance, insurance, and financial education. Employing a descriptive-correlational research design, data were collected from 337 members of six cooperatives categorized as small, medium, and large, using a validated survey instrument. Findings indicate high member satisfaction with cooperative loan services, particularly credit and savings accounts, emphasizing their role in enhancing financial accessibility and stability. Members strongly agree that these services contribute to improved income generation, asset acquisition, and overall well-being. Additionally, a significant positive relationship between cooperative loan services and the sustainability of livelihood programs was identified. The study also highlights challenges faced by cooperative managers, such as resource limitations and operational complexities, providing insights for strategic improvements. This research underscores the essential role of cooperatives in fostering inclusive economic growth and community development. It offers practical recommendations for policymakers, cooperative leaders, and development practitioners to strengthen cooperative frameworks and enhance the sustainability of livelihood programs.

Keywords: *Cooperatives, Loan Services, Sustainability, Livelihood Programs, Tacurong City*

INTRODUCTION

Cooperatives play a pivotal role in providing financial services that support livelihood programs, particularly in marginalized communities. According to Berdegué et al. (2013), cooperatives contribute significantly to economic inclusivity by offering accessible financial services such as credit, savings, microfinance, insurance, and financial education. Similarly, Nathan et al. (2004) emphasized that cooperatives provide financial and non-financial services to low-income individuals, allowing them to improve their economic conditions. In Tacurong City, cooperatives serve as alternative financial institutions that provide accessible financial services, especially for those excluded from traditional banking systems.

Globally, cooperatives have emerged as powerful tools for socioeconomic development, fostering solidarity, and addressing inequality across diverse regions. From the agricultural cooperatives of Africa that ensure food security to the credit unions in North America providing accessible financial services, these organizations have proven their resilience and adaptability in meeting local and global challenges. The International Cooperative Alliance estimates that over one billion people worldwide are members of cooperatives, contributing significantly to sustainable development and the global economy. As collaborative enterprises rooted in shared values, cooperatives demonstrate the strength of collective action in addressing the world's pressing socioeconomic issues, inspiring nations like the Philippines to harness their potential for inclusive growth (CDA, 1991).

Cooperatives have a long and significant history in the Philippines, reflecting the country's commitment to community-based economic development. These organizations adhere to cooperative principles, including voluntary and open membership, democratic control, economic participation, and concern for the community. In the Philippines, cooperatives operate across various sectors, such as agriculture, credit, and consumer goods, and have played a crucial role in empowering marginalized communities and fostering economic inclusivity (Berdegué et al., 2013).

According to Montgomery and Weiss (2005), one of the primary advantages of cooperatives is their ability to provide small-scale financial services, including micro-loans and savings plans, to individuals who lack access to formal financial institutions. These financial services are crucial in enhancing the economic resilience of cooperative members. Similarly, Risal (2020) noted that cooperatives are formed to support and uplift their members' living standards by offering credit, insurance, and other financial services tailored to local community needs. Furthermore, Pradhan (2016) emphasized that microfinance cooperatives play a vital role in economic inclusion, particularly in rural and underserved areas, by equipping members with essential financial literacy and training programs.

The provision of financial services, particularly loan services, by cooperatives plays a pivotal role in enhancing the socio-economic conditions of their members. This study examines the cooperative loan services in Tacurong City and their impact on the

sustainability of livelihood programs. Cooperative societies, often deeply ingrained in local communities, are essential to economic development and empowerment. As microfinance institutions, they contribute significantly to poverty alleviation, offering members access to affordable credit and savings opportunities, which, in turn, stimulate economic growth (Bateman, 2010; Armendariz & Morduch, 2010).

Furthermore, cooperative societies in the Philippines have been commended for uplifting marginalized and vulnerable groups, serving as viable alternatives to traditional banking institutions (Berdegué et al., 2013). A livelihood is considered sustainable if it can withstand shocks and strains, recover from them, and preserve or improve its resources and capacities without compromising the availability of natural resources. Krantz (2001) explained that sustainable livelihoods require economic stability, resilience to external shocks, and an inclusive approach that considers multiple dimensions of poverty beyond income levels. The engagement of cooperative members in sustainable livelihood programs enhances the effectiveness of such initiatives.

Beck et al. (2007) emphasized that institutional environment quality, credit access, and financial infrastructure significantly influence financial outreach and depth. Effective infrastructure services have a major impact on market development and economic production growth (Malhotra, 2017). Policies promoting financial inclusion are particularly successful in reaching underprivileged populations, rural communities, women, and young people (Allen et al., 2016). However, achieving sustainability is a complex, long-term process requiring strategic planning and institutional support (Ferguson, 2012).

Several studies have underscored the connection between access to financial services and improved livelihood sustainability (Duflo et al., 2013; Karlan & Morduch, 2010). Despite this, the specific effects of cooperative loan services on livelihood programs in Tacurong City remain underexplored. Understanding this relationship is vital not only for cooperative members but also for policymakers and development organizations seeking to implement effective poverty reduction strategies.

This study aims to bridge the existing research gap by examining the loan services provided by cooperatives in Tacurong City and assessing the sustainability of their livelihood programs. By conducting a comprehensive investigation, the researchers aim to generate insights that can inform policy decisions, enhance cooperative strategies, and contribute to the overall economic development of the region. This research builds upon existing literature while offering practical recommendations for cooperative societies, local government agencies, and development practitioners to strengthen cooperative frameworks and improve socioeconomic outcomes.

Research Questions

The study determined the relationship between cooperatives' loan services and the sustainability of the livelihood programs of their members. It answered the following questions:

1. What is the extent of the implementation of loan services by cooperatives in Tacurong City in terms of:
 - 1.1 credit services;
 - 1.2 savings accounts;
 - 1.3 microfinance services;
 - 1.4 insurance services; and
 - 1.5 financial education and training?
2. What is the extent of sustainability of livelihood programs offered by cooperatives among their members in terms of:
 - 2.1 economic sustainability;
 - 2.2 social sustainability;
 - 2.3 environmental sustainability;
 - 2.4. physical sustainability; and,
 - 2.5. institutional sustainability?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the loan services provided by cooperatives and the sustainability of livelihood programs among their members in Tacurong City?
4. What challenges do the Board of Directors and cooperative managers encounter in managing cooperatives in Tacurong City?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to examine the relationship between cooperative loan services and the sustainability of livelihood programs. Data were collected from 337 cooperative members across six cooperatives, categorized as small, medium, and large cooperatives in Tacurong City. The selection criteria included active cooperative membership and direct involvement in livelihood programs.

A self-made questionnaire was the primary data collection tool, divided into three sections: (1) demographic information, (2) cooperative loan services, and (3) sustainability of livelihood programs. The questionnaire underwent validation by experts, followed by a pilot test to refine the instrument before distribution.

The survey was conducted over four weeks, ensuring broad participation among members. Statistical tools such as mean, standard deviation, and Pearson correlation were employed to analyze the data.

RESULTS

Summary on Loan Services of Cooperatives

Table 1 presents the summary of the loan services of cooperatives in Tacurong City, Sultan Kudarat, particularly on credit services, savings accounts, microfinance services, insurance services, and financial education and training.

Table 1. Summary on loan services of cooperatives in Tacurong City, Sultan Kudarat

Loan Services	Standard Deviation (SD)	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
Credit Services	0.74	4.47	Strongly Agree	The cooperatives are extremely determined in the implementation of their loan services among its members
Saving Account	0.77	4.38	Strongly Agree	The cooperatives are extremely determined in the implementation of their loan services among its members
Microfinance Services	0.95	4.19	Agree	The cooperatives are determined in the implementation of their loan services among their members
Insurance Services	0.83	4.26	Strongly Agree	The cooperatives are extremely determined in the implementation of their loan services among its members
Financial and Education Training	0.91	4.24	Strongly Agree	The cooperatives are extremely determined in the implementation of their loan services among its members
Mean	0.84	4.31	Strongly Agree	The cooperatives are extremely determined in the implementation of their loan services among its members

Summary on Sustainability of Livelihood Program

Table 2 presents the analysis of the sustainability of the cooperative's livelihood program, highlighting the perceptions of cooperative members regarding various dimensions of sustainability, including economic, social, environmental, physical, and institutional sustainability.

Table 2 Sustainability of Livelihood Program, Tacurong City, Sultan Kudarat, September 2024.

Sustainability of Livelihood Program	Standard Deviation (SD)	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
Economic Sustainability	0.99	4.03	Agree	The cooperatives are religiously working on the sustainability of their livelihood programs
Social Sustainability	0.98	4.11	Agree	The cooperatives are religiously working on the sustainability of their livelihood programs
Environmental Sustainability	1.00	4.12	Agree	The cooperatives are religiously working on the sustainability of their livelihood programs
Physical Sustainability	0.88	4.34	Strongly Agree	The cooperatives are extremely working on the sustainability of their livelihood programs
Institutional Sustainability	1.26	4.13	Agree	The cooperatives are religiously working on the sustainability of their livelihood programs
Mean	1.02	4.14	Agree	The cooperatives are religiously working on the sustainability of their livelihood programs

Correlation Between Loan Services and Livelihood Sustainability Programs of Cooperatives

The following table presents the correlation between the loan services and livelihood sustainability programs of the cooperatives in Tacurong City, Sultan Kudarat.

Correlation between loan services and livelihood sustainability programs

Paired variables	Pearson-r Correlation	Interpretation
Loan services & livelihood sustainability	0.51	Moderate positive, Significant

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 level of significance

Top 5 challenges encountered by the Board of Directors and Cooperative Managers in Managing Cooperatives in Tacurong City, Sultan Kudarat

Table 3 presents the top five challenges faced by the cooperative, as identified by the respondents. These challenges are ranked based on the frequency of responses.

Table 3. Top 5 Challenges encountered by the Board of Directors and Cooperative Managers in Managing Cooperatives

Challenges	Ranking
1. Shortages/lack of loanable budgets	1
2. Difficulty in digital services of the cooperatives.	2
3. Difficulty in imposing discipline among delinquent members.	3
4. Challenges in increasing the number of cooperative members.	4
5. Difficulty in implementing the mandated functions of the cooperatives.	5

Conclusions

This study sought to assess the extent of cooperative loan services and their impact on the sustainability of livelihood programs in Tacurong City. Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn in response to the research questions:

1. Cooperative loan services, mainly credit services and savings accounts, are highly accessible and significantly contribute to members' financial stability and

empowerment. However, improvements in microfinance, insurance services, and financial literacy programs can further enhance their effectiveness.

2. The sustainability of livelihood programs among cooperative members is evident in economic, social, environmental, physical, and institutional aspects. Among these, physical sustainability ranked highest, while economic sustainability scored the lowest, indicating a need for better financial security measures.
3. A significant positive correlation exists between cooperative loan services and livelihood program sustainability, affirming that financial accessibility through cooperatives enhances long-term economic and social stability.
4. Challenges such as limited loanable funds, difficulties in digitalization, enforcement of discipline among delinquent members, limited outreach efforts, and compliance with mandated regulations hinder cooperative growth and sustainability. Addressing these challenges is essential for optimizing cooperative effectiveness.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study regarding loan services offered by cooperatives in Tacurong City, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Enhancement of Financial Literacy Programs:** Cooperatives should strengthen their financial education and training initiatives to equip members with better financial management skills, ultimately improving economic sustainability.
2. **Expansion of Loanable Funds and Microfinance Services:** Cooperative leaders should explore alternative funding sources, partnerships, and government support to increase available capital for loans and expand microfinance opportunities.
3. **Improved Risk Protection and Insurance Coverage:** Introducing more comprehensive and accessible insurance services will provide cooperative members with better financial security and resilience against economic shocks.
4. **Strengthening Governance and Digitalization Efforts:** Cooperatives should invest in digital solutions to streamline operations, improve financial tracking, and enhance accessibility of services.
5. **Future Research Recommendations:** Further studies should be conducted using larger samples or a comparative approach with other regions to validate findings. Additionally, qualitative research exploring members' lived experiences may provide deeper insights into cooperative impact.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers of this study ensured full compliance with ethical standards in conducting this research. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents before their participation, and they were given the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. The anonymity of all respondents was strictly maintained, and their personal information was kept confidential in accordance with data privacy regulations. The well-being of the participants was safeguarded throughout the study, ensuring that no harm, discomfort, or undue pressure was exerted upon them.

Furthermore, the researchers affirm that there were no conflicts of interest in the conduct of this study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all sources were properly cited in accordance with academic integrity guidelines. The interpretation of the findings was conducted without bias, ensuring objectivity and reliability. The results of this study are used solely for research purposes, contributing to the academic and practical discourse on cooperative loan services and livelihood sustainability.

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